

EVALUATION OF THE STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR AT A T-SHAPED CRACK LOCATED AT THE INTERFACE OF TWO BONDED STRIPS BY THE OPTICAL METHOD OF CAUSTICS

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ABSTRACT

One of the basic crack problems in composite materials, that is, a T-shaped crack located at the bimaterial interface is investigated experimentally by means of the optical method of caustics. The T-shaped crack consists of the interface crack and the perpendicular crack. A new experimental method for the bimaterial interface crack is developed to obtain the stress intensity factors. It uses the transverse and longitudinal sizes of caustics instead of two distances between and points of each caustic curve. This method is applied to a T-shaped crack at the interface between two sectionally bonded epoxy strips with different material constants. Present experimental results are compared with the previous theoretical ones.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials consist of the matrix and the fiber with the diameter and volume content of about 0.01mm and 30 to 50%, respectively. Thus, the interface between constituents has a significant role in various aspects of the strength of composite materials. For example, the fracture process in composites is quite complicated compared to the previous structural materials due to the interface. Usually it exhibits a variety of failure modes such as fiber breaking, matrix cracking, debonding and delamination even in a small fractured area. It is supposed that a small crack initiating in either one of constituents propagates and hits the interface at the early stage of the fracture. The interface may arrest it, keep up the propagation into the other medium, or deviate it into debonding or delamination along the interface itself as a T-shaped crack (see Fig.1). Each process depends on the mechanical properties of the matrix and fiber and also their interface. The T-shaped crack could also be seen macroscopically at the final stage of fracture in laminates. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the mechanical characteristics of the T-shaped crack

Fig.1 A model specimen for a T-shaped crack at the interface in composites (mm).

Fig.2 Optical analysis of a caustics.

for the profound understanding of the strength of composite materials. Many efforts have been made on this subject [1-3] theoretically. There is no experimental report on this subject within the knowledge of authors.

In this paper, the stress intensity factors at the T-shaped crack tips will be obtained experimentally with the use of the optical method of caustics. First, a new method to handle the caustics is presented. It is effective to a bimaterial interface crack. The previous technique used two distances between end points of each caustics curve. In practice, it is quite difficult to locate these points in the case of a bimaterial interface crack. Here, both transverse and longitudinal sizes of caustics are used. Next, this method is applied to two types of bimaterial T-shaped crack to obtain the stress intensity factors. Finally, these factors are compared with the theoretical values [1], which shows the acceptable capability of the present experimental method.

2. CAUSTIC EQUATION AND STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS

A light beam passing through a transparent plate near the crack tip under loading is deviated by the variation of thickness and refractive index of the plate as shown in Fig.2. Consequently, a strongly illuminated curve appears on a screen as the caustics. Basic equations for the caustics with nomenclatures in Fig.2 are as follows [4],

$$\bar{r}' = \lambda_m \bar{r} - z_o t c_o \text{grad}[(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) \pm \xi(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)], \quad \lambda_m = \frac{z_o + z_i}{z_i} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial x'}{\partial r} \frac{\partial y'}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\partial x'}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial y'}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where t is the plate thickness and c_o and ξ are stress optical constants of the plate. Moreover, σ_1 and σ_2 are principal stresses near the crack tip and can be expressed in term of the stress intensity factors k_i . Thus, the caustic curves yield the stress intensity factors using Eqs.(1) and (2).

A bimaterial interface crack tip has the singularity of both opening and in-plane sliding modes in general. Therefore, its caustic curves are rather complicated than the opening mode case as shown in Fig.3, where two pairs of caustics in solid and dotted lines are obtained in case of a non-vanishing ξ . The vanishing ξ turns two pairs into one pair. The above equations do not yield the simple explicit relation between k_i and the representative values of caustic curves, being different from the opening mode with a quite simple relation between k_1 and D_1 . Theocaris [3] used two distances, AB and CD. However, it is quite difficult to measure them.

Here, a new method using the transverse and longitudinal global sizes, D_1 and D_2 , is proposed. It is shown numerically that D_2/D_1 is a function of $\eta = k_1/k_2$ in practice within the wide range of k_2 as shown in Fig.4. We can obtain the relation between D_1 and k_2 for each η , too. The present process is as follows. First, D_1 and D_2 are mea-

(a) Opening mode (b) Mixed mode
Fig.3 Caustics in epoxy specimen (see Table 1).

Fig.4 D_2/D_1 as a function of $-\eta (= -k_1/k_2)$

Table 1 Material constants.

Epoxy	Young's modulus $E(\text{kg/mm}^2)$	Poisson's ratio ν	Stress optical coefficient $c'_o(\text{mm}^2/\text{kg}\cdot 10^{-3})$	Coefficient of optical anisotropy
A	334.50	0.35	-1.04	0.26
B	201.50	-0.38	-2.05	0.12

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The specimens are 4mm thick and made of two sectionally bonded epoxy strips with various crack lengths, a and b . Material constants are given in Table 1. Two types of Young's modulus ratio are provided. The interface crack tip in Fig. 1 closes under tension due to the Poisson's effect. Thus, the compressive load P is used to obtain k_1 and k_2 at the interface crack tip of a specimen-C with a little wider perpendicular slit. The k_1 at the perpendicular crack tip is obtained under tension T from a specimen-T with a little wider interface slit. These slits are checked not to close in the experiment. Figure 5 shows the optical arrangement. A He-Ne laser light beam was used. The z_o and z_i are set to be about 2m and 1m, respectively. Caustic curves on the screen were photographed at each loading step as shown in Fig. 6. Two pairs of open curves are formed around each crack tip as predicted in Fig. 3. Figure 7 shows the present stress intensity factors in solid lines. They are in good agreement with the previous theoretical ones [1]. This is the first experimental verification to these problems within the knowledge of authors and shows that the present experimental method is acceptable.

4. CONCLUSION

1. A new experimental technique for the bimaterial interface crack is proposed, using the optical method of caustics.
2. Stress intensity factors of a T-shaped crack at the bimaterial interface in composites are obtained. These are in good agreement with the previous theoretical values.

This work was carried out as a part of the dissertation of the first author at the Research Institute for Applied Mechanics, Kyushu University. We are grateful to Professors K. Takahashi and K. Kawatate for their valuable discussions.

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Fig. 5 Optical arrangement.

sured from the caustic curves on the screen. Figure 4 yields k_1/k_2 for each D_2/D_1 . The relation between D_1 and k_2 for the fixed k_1/k_2 is used to obtain k_2 . Finally, k_1 is determined. The detailed numerical processes are presented in [4].

(a) P=200kgf (b) T=50kgf
 Fig.6 Caustics at (a) interface and (b) perpendicular crack of a bimaterial T-shaped crack.

(a) interface crack (b) perpendicular crack
 Fig.7 Stress intensity factors.